

STRUCTURES AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF
CENTRIFUGALLY CAST SiC/Al COMPOSITES

M. N. Gungor
Westinghouse Science and Technology Center
Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania 15235

A. H. Nakagawa
Westinghouse Marine Division
Sunnyvale, California 94088

S. D. Karmarkar and A. P. Divecha
Naval Surface Warfare Center
Silver Spring, Maryland 20903

ABSTRACT

The structures and mechanical properties of SiC-A356 Al particulate reinforced composites were characterized. The composite samples were fabricated using a centrifugal casting method. Because of the density difference between the SiC particles and the Al matrix, the denser SiC particles segregated preferentially in the outer regions of the samples during centrifugal casting and solidification. The macro- and microstructures of the cast samples were characterized to determine the extent of the SiC particle segregation. The room temperature tension and compression properties of the cast specimens obtained from the segregated layers were established. The results showed that a range of mechanical properties can be obtained as a function of microstructure, and overall, the strength and modulus of the composite layers were superior to those of the corresponding unreinforced Al layers.

KEYWORDS: Metal Matrix Composites; Centrifugal Casting; Solidification; Tension/Compression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compared to monolithic aluminum alloys, particulate reinforced aluminum-based composites offer a 10 to 25 % increase in strength and a 30 to 80% increase in stiffness. Because these composites are stiffer than their

monolithic counterparts, stiffness limited components can be designed using reduced cross sections and attendant reductions in component weights.

Centrifugal casting offers an economical means of processing controlled composite structures which makes it an attractive processing route for the production of particulate reinforced tubes.(1-3) The rotation of the casting during solidification causes the components of the composite melt to segregate, and subsequently solidify into well defined layered structures. The process can be controlled to drive the denser particles such as SiC toward the outer regions of the less dense Al matrix alloy. In this way, the particulate loading can be increased in the outer layers of the tube with concomitant increases in stiffness in this region. In addition, the centrifugally cast structures solidify in relatively short times, thereby, improving production rates. Furthermore, the resultant structures are sounder than those of conventionally cast structures, thereby producing better mechanical properties. Moreover, the lightweight impurities and porosity can be driven toward the inner surface of the casting where they can be subsequently machined away. Finally, since the castings do not have large risers (except at the inner surface which effectively acts as a riser) the scrap rate is low compared to other foundry methods. This provides an added cost benefit by reducing the cost of raw materials for the already low cost process.

Centrifugal casting processing of the metal matrix composites was therefore investigated as a cost effective, innovative means of producing high integrity, high stiffness structural tubes. This investigation demonstrated the use of centrifugal casting to produce controlled structures in SiC-A356 Al composites on a laboratory scale. The structure and room temperature tension and compression properties of the samples produced were evaluated and correlated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Materials Used Unreinforced A356 Al alloy and SiC particle reinforced A356 Al alloy composites were used. The unreinforced Al alloy ingots were purchased from Belmont Metals Inc., Brooklyn, NY; whereas, the composite materials were procured from the Dural Aluminum Composites Corporation, San Diego, CA.

2.2 Sample Fabrication The samples of 10 cm OD, 5 cm ID and 13 cm long were fabricated using a horizontal centrifugal casting machine and an experimental test matrix. The experimental test matrix was a statistical design of experiments to study the centrifugal casting variables which are not discussed in this paper. Melting of materials was achieved in a resistance heated furnace. The melt was then removed from the furnace and immediately poured into a rotating mold at a designated speed. The mold was rotated until solidification of the casting was complete. The mold was then arrested, and the casting extracted from the mold for evaluation.

2.3 Structure Characterization The macro- and microstructures of the cast samples were evaluated in the transverse and longitudinal directions of the castings. The macrostructures were revealed by grinding the samples with SiC particle embedded papers (up to 600 grit size paper) with water lubrication in a semi-automatic polishing machine. Continuing polishing with the diamond pastes (9, 6, and 1 μm diamond pastes) and an oil lubricant, and etching with 5% HF solution revealed the material microstructures.

The extent of the SiC particle segregation was quantified using three techniques; wet chemical analysis, segregation ratio determination, and point count technique. First, sample chips were drilled out from the segregated layers. The material chips were then analyzed using a standard wet chemical analysis procedure developed at the Dural Aluminum Composites Corporation, San Diego, CA, to determine the ratio of the SiC particulate to the alloy in the sample. Second, by macroscopically observing the segregated layers of the casting we measured the thicknesses of the SiC depleted layer and of the SiC enriched layer. We then defined a dimensionless "segregation ratio" term to express the extent of the SiC segregation on a comparative basis. The segregation ratio, S, an arbitrary definition, is given by:

$$S = 1 - (R_m/R_c)^2 \quad (1)$$

where R_m is the measured outer radius of the metal rich layer, and R_c is the outer radius of the casting. The significance of this term is that as S decreases, the severity of the segregation increases. The distribution of the SiC particles was obtained as a function of the radial distance using a quantitative point count technique developed by Hilliard and Cahn (4).

2.4 Tension and Compression Testing Flat tensile specimens were machined from the SiC enriched layers of the cast samples parallel to the axial direction of the castings. Diamond tooling was used to machine the composite specimens. The composite specimens were heat treated after machining to either the T6 condition or the T61 condition. Tension and compression tests were conducted at room temperature per ASTM D3552 and ASTM E9 in a Satec universal testing machine, model 30WBN. The tensile strain was measured with a 25.4 mm gage length extensometer. Cylindrical compression specimens of 6.4 mm OD and 19 mm long were machined from the SiC enriched layers of the cast samples in the axial direction. Compressive 0.2% off-set yield strength and modulus were obtained with an extensometer of 12.7 mm gage length. Due to the limitation imposed by the specimen geometry, deformation above the yield point was monitored by the load vs. crosshead displacement output of the testing machine. The tension and compression tests speeds were 0.042 cm/s. Two tests were conducted per material condition.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Casting Morphology Figure 1 shows the typical cast samples of 10 vol% SiC-A356 Al. Although each specimen was produced with the different process variables, these two figures show two distinct groups of the samples. The first group of the samples, the four samples on the left hand side of the pictures, were produced with a thermally conducting mold (graphite coated steel mold). The second group of the samples, the four samples on the right hand side of the pictures, were produced with a thermally insulating mold (alumina coated steel mold).

Figure 1 — Overview of the 10 vol% SiC/A356 Al composite cast samples (OD= 10 cm).

Some of readily observable characteristics of the samples shown are that the samples produced with the conducting mold have metallic, smooth and

inhomogeneous surfaces. On the other hand, the samples produced with the insulating molds have rough and homogeneous surfaces.

The thermally conductive mold increases the rate of heat transfer from the casting to the mold. In this situation, due to relatively rapid heat removal from the castings, the surfaces of the castings contained traces of the rapidly solidified droplets and progressive traces of the molten metal flow. Therefore, the castings were produced with inhomogeneous surfaces because of enhanced heat transfer from the casting to the mold.

In the case of insulating mold, however, the reduced heat transfer rate from the casting to the mold allows the molten metal to flow freely (i.e., without pre-mature solidification) and cover the mold's inner surface completely before solidifying. Droplets that impinged on the mold ahead of the major flow of the liquid, either did not solidify on contact or were remelted by the major flow of the molten metal. Therefore, the insulating mold produced homogeneous surfaces by reducing heat transfer rate from the casting to the mold. Further evidence to support this mechanism will be presented following the materials macrostructure characterization.

3.2 Macrostructures The transverse macrostructures of the samples are shown in Figure 2 as a function of the initial composite composition and the mold thermal properties. Each of the macrostructures shows two layers; a segregated composite (SiC particle rich) outer layer, and a metal inner layer. The two layers were separated by a well defined interface. The thicknesses of the segregated layers in the samples produced with the conducting mold are greater than the corresponding samples produced with the insulating mold, i.e., more severe SiC particle segregation was produced in the latter case.

The longitudinal macrostructures of the samples produced with the two molds showed that the thickness of the segregated layer was more uniform in the insulating mold case than in the conducting mold. Typical macrostructures of the two cases are shown in Figure 3. The darkness of the SiC particle segregated layer is proportional to the SiC concentration, i.e., the darker the layer, the higher the SiC concentration. Figure 3 shows that the sample produced with the insulating mold has uniform contrast along the longitudinal and radial directions, whereas the corresponding conducting mold case, shows non-

Figure 2 — Macrostructures of the transverse sections of the samples produced with the conducting mold (above) and the insulating mold (below) (OD = 10 cm).

Figure 3 — Macrostructures of the longitudinal cross section of the samples produced using the conducting (above) and insulating (below) molds (Length: 13 cm).

uniform contrast, in the longitudinal and radial directions, an indication that the SiC distribution is more homogeneous in the former.

3.3 Modelling A physical model based on the observations presented thus far is proposed as follows. Droplets form at the molten metal front as it enters the spinning mold. A thermally conducting mold does not retard heat transfer from the casting. Due to rapid heat removal through the mold the droplets solidify instantly as they impinged on the mold surface. Then, as the molten metal front covers the inner surface of the mold (i.e., as it flows from entrance of the mold to the far end) it solidifies progressively on contact with the mold surface, thus, resulting

in the flow traces observed on the casting surfaces (Figure 1) and in the internal structures (Figure 3). Because heat is removed from the progressive layers at such a fast rate, it does not re-melt the droplets, and the droplets are covered by the progressively solidified layers. The conducting mold, thus, provides an inhomogeneous surface and internal structure by enhancing heat transfer from the casting at the mold/metal interface and thus causing local freezing before the entire mold inner surface has been covered by molten metal. This physical model is illustrated in Figure 4.

The insulating mold delays transfer of heat from the castings and allows the molten metal to flow freely (i.e., without premature solidification) and to cover the mold inner surface. Any molten droplets that solidify ahead of the liquid flow are remelted as they are covered by the molten layer filling the mold. Once the mold surface is covered by molten metal, the solidification proceeds in the radial direction. The insulating mold, thus, provides a homogeneous surface and internal structure by delaying

Figure 4 — Physical models for centrifugal casting and solidification process as a function of mold thermal properties.

heat transfer from the casting at the mold/metal interface until the mold inner surface has been covered by the molten metal. The physical model for this case is also illustrated in Figure 4.

3.4 Microstructures Typical optical microstructures of the centrifugal castings are presented in Figures 5 and 6, for the conducting and insulating molds, respectively. In each figure, the transverse micrographs are shown as a function of radial distance. As expected,

Figure 5 — Microstructures of the sample produced using the 10 vol% SiC/A356 Al in the conducting mold.

the SiC particles were inhomogeneously distributed in the microstructures in Figure 5, and were more homogeneously distributed in the microstructures in Figure 6. In both cases, the microstructure of the inner metal layer is predominately equiaxed dendrites. Typical Al-Si eutectic phase was located within the dendritic spaces. In the SiC segregated regions, the dendritic morphology is less obvious, particularly for the case of the insulating mold. More microporosity is observed to be associated with the SiC particles in the insulating mold.

3.5 SiC Segregation

3.5.1 Chemical Analysis The results of the wet chemical analysis are given in Table 1. The outer layer SiC composition is plotted in Figure 7 (left) which shows two groups of data: those produced with the

Figure 6 — Microstructures of the sample produced using the 10 vol% SiC/A356 Al in the insulating mold.

conducting mold and those produced with the insulating mold. As listed in Table 2, the average SiC composition of the former samples was 11.9 vol%, while that of the latter samples was 24.8 vol%. Considering that the initial composition contained an average of 10 vol% SiC, the centrifugal casting process increased the SiC composition by factors of approximately 1.2 and 2.5, respectively.

3.5.2 Segregation Ratio The segregation ratio measurements are given in Table 2, and the data are plotted in Figure 7 (right) for the 10 vol% SiC initial composition. In an analogous manner to the previous chemical analysis results, the segregation ratio also depended strongly on the mold type. The average segregation ratios of the samples produced with the 10 vol% SiC initial compositions were 0.52 and 0.25 for the conducting mold and insulating mold, respectively.

3.5.3 SiC Distribution The results of the point count experiments are shown in Figure 8 for two samples that were produced using the 10 vol% SiC initial composition, and the conducting and insulating molds. The vol% SiC data are plotted against radial distance. The average composition of the segregated regions were 25.6 vol% SiC and 11.2 vol% SiC, respectively. These data agree very well with the results of the wet chemical analysis.

3.6 Tension and Compression Testing The data for the tension and compression tests are given in Tables 3 and 4, for the A356 Al, 10 vol% SiC/A356 Al, and 20 vol% SiC/A356 Al samples. An analysis of the data as a function of the material microstructure is given as follows.

Figure 7 — SiC segregation by wet chemical analysis (left) and by segregation ratio measurement (right).

Table 1 — SiC Vol Pct Measured by Wet Chemical Analysis - Initial Composition: 10 vol% SiC

<u>Specimen #</u>	<u>Mold Type</u>	<u>SiC vol% Outer Layer</u>	<u>SiC vol% Inner Layer</u>
10	Conducting	12.1	1.2
12	"	11.2	1.2
7	"	12.4	1.3
Average	Conducting	11.9 ± 0.6	1.2 ± 0.6
14	Insulating	23.9	0.3
18	"	25.8	0.3
Average	Insulating	24.8 ± 1.3	0.3 ± 0

The only effect of the thermal properties of the molds on the tensile and compressive properties of the unreinforced A356 Al was that the tensile ductility was higher by a factor of two in the case of the insulating mold. However, in the case of the 10 vol% SiC initial composition, the composite samples produced with the insulating mold showed higher tensile yield strengths and compressive strengths as shown in Figure 9. The average tensile yield strengths values were of 215±14 MPa and 254±15 MPa, respectively. Thus, there was approximately 17% increase in tensile yield

strength for the insulating mold over the conducting mold. Similarly, the compressive yield strengths of the 10 vol% SiC composition averaged about 226±10 MPa and 257±23 MPa for the conducting and insulating molds, respectively.

Table 2 — Segregation Ratio Measurements
Initial Composition: 10 vol% SiC

Factorial Experiment #	Specimen #	Mold Type	Segregation Ratio $1 - (R_m/R_c)^2$
1	10	C	0.54
2	14	I	0.29
3	12	C	0.55
4	18	I	0.24
5	23	C	0.51
6	16	I	0.24
7	7	C	0.47
8	22	I	0.26

Average segregation ratio of "all C" = 0.52 ± 0.03

Average segregation ratio of "all I" = 0.25 ± 0.02

C = Conducting Mold I = Insulating Mold

Figure 8 — SiC volume per cent distribution as a function of radial distance for two samples produced with the conducting and insulating molds.

The effects of the composition on the tensile and compressive strengths are presented in Figure 10. The mean effect of composition on the tensile yield strength, was determined by averaging the data points that fell into each individual composition group; 0 vol% SiC, 10 vol% SiC, and 20 vol% SiC. As the lines drawn in Figure 10 clearly show, the average tensile yield strength increased as the composition increased. The average yield strengths were 164±10 MPa, 242±24 MPa, and 292±18 MPa for the 0 vol% SiC, 10 vol% SiC, and 20 vol% SiC compositions, respectively. As in the case of the tensile response, the compressive strength increased as the composition increased. As given in Tables 3 and 4, the tensile and compression moduli increased as the SiC composition increased. For example, the average tensile moduli calculated were 71.6 ± 11 GPa, 101.2 ±

13.1 GPa and 127.5 ± 20 GPa, for the 0 vol% SiC, 10 vol% SiC and 20 vol% SiC, respectively. In all cases, the tensile elongation of the composites was on the order of 1% or less (Table 3). Note that the scatter in the data for the 0 vol% SiC composition was minimal, while the scatter in the data for the 10 vol% SiC and 20 vol% SiC compositions was much greater. This clearly indicates that the composite materials are much more sensitive to process variables than the unreinforced A356 Al.

Figure 9 — The effects of the mold properties on the tensile and compression properties.

Table 3 — Tensile Properties of A356 Al and SiC/A356 Al Composites

Specimen #	Composition (Vol% SiC)	Material Condition	0.2% Offset Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Elongation (%)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
6	0	C/T6	174±0	255±11	5.3±1.7	70
6	"	C/Hip+T6	168±6	280±0	13.3±1.8	73
17	"	I/T6	151±12	259±7	10.6±1.1	64
17	"	I/Hip+T6	162±3	276±2	16.5±2.1	80±18
10	10	C/T6	221±20	242±4	0.6±0.1	94±7
10	"	C/Hip+T6	248±0	256±0	0.7±0.4	94±1
10	"	C/Hip+T61	182±4	252±48	2.2±2.0	102±14
14	"	I/T6	241±5	255±10	0.6±0.1	91±15
14	"	I/Hip+T6	274±9	313±17	0.7±0.4	102±23
14	"	I/Hip+T61	208±2	246±43	0.8±0.3	98±13
23	"	C/T6	212±8	285±4	3.2±0.2	89±1
23	"	C/Hip+T6	219±6	289±20	2.4±1.4	100±25
23	"	C/Hip+T61	169±1	244±20	2.7±1.9	94±5
16	"	I/T6	255±16	293±2	0.8±0.3	109±13
16	"	I/Hip+T6	268±20	332±16	1.2±0.0	122±5
16	"	I/Hip+T61	209±16	255±20	1.1±0.8	104±8
24	20	C/T6	279±12	326±6	0.9±0.0	116±30
26	"	I/T6	304±26	330±43	0.6±0.1	129±37
27	"	I/T6	310±17	353±14	0.7±0.0	144±12
29	"	I/T6	277±3	316±4	0.8±0.0	121±5

HIP: At 500°C for 4 hours under 100 MPa Argon pressure

T6: Solution treatment at 537°C in air for 4 hours, quench in water at 85°C, age at 155°C for 4 hours

T61: Same as T6 but age at 25°C

C: Conducting mold

I: Insulating Mold

The tensile properties and the compressive properties of the 10 vol% SiC initial composition were affected by the heat treatments. In general, the yield strengths were greater after the T6 treatment than after the T61 treatment. This result can be rationalized on the basis of matrix strengthening, i.e., the T6 treatment increases the strength of the matrix by the precipitation hardening.

In general terms, the HIP process improved the tensile and compressive strengths of the all of the materials. Its effect on the tensile and compressive moduli was, however, insignificant. HIP improved the tensile ductility of the unreinforced A356 by 50-100% (Table 3), though its effect on the tensile ductility of the composite materials was again insignificant. The increase in the compressive strength, particularly for the composite specimens, can be attributed to a reduction in microporosity due to HIP. Absolute increases in properties were not very high due to the fact that the starting porosity levels were generally quite low (1% or less).

Table 4 — Compressive Properties of A356 Al and SiC/A356 Al Composites

Specimen #	Composition (Vol% SiC)	Material Condition	0.2% Offset Yield Strength (MPa)	Compressive Strength at 10% Deformation (MPa)	Compressive Strength at 20% Deformation (MPa)	Compressive Modulus (GPa)
6	0	C/T6	179*12	356	456	78
6	"	C/Hip+T6	190*3	353*4	453*7	79
17	"	I/T6	172*3	334*8	434*11	72
17	"	I/Hip+T6	181*3	353*8	460*11	71*2
10	10	C/T6	220*10	406*31	489*19	90
10	"	C/Hip+T6	259*2	480*2	535*3	103*14
10	"	C/Hip+T61	188*6	426*29	541	108*16
14	"	I/T6	238*2	459*2	525*5	117*2
14	"	I/Hip+T6	288*0	526*4	578*9	111*4
14	"	I/Hip+T61	216*8	494*2	580*2	97
23	"	C/T6	233*5	439*8	513*3	96*3
23	"	C/Hip+T6	248*0	480*9	533*14	97*13
23	"	C/Hip+T61	175*12	409*20	487*48	101*17
16	"	I/T6	277*4	515*10	553*9	112*20
16	"	I/Hip+T6	282*2	530*2	587*5	111*11
16	"	I/T61	201*10	482*18	532*18	117*7
16	"	I/Hip+T61	223*4	496*1	571*6	108*15
24	20	C/T6	298*1	544*2	-	132*21
26	"	I/T6	343*5	611*16	635	132*1
27	"	I/T6	324*17	618*2	618*2	140*33
29	"	I/T6	297*5	540*12	571	119*12

Figure 10 — The effects of the composition on the tensile and compressive properties.

All of the composite tensile failures were typical of brittle failures where the fracture generally occurred perpendicular to the testing

direction. Unlike the unreinforced A356 Al, which failed in a very ductile manner, the composite materials' failures show no evidence of gross plasticity. Plastic deformation of the matrix did occur locally and could be observed on the fracture surfaces (Figure 11). The fracture surfaces of the composite materials also show "extensive particle fractures" which is evidence of a strong SiC/Al interface. This in turn is consistent with the high tensile modulus data. Almost all specimens were free from the macroscopic defects (particle clusters, intermetallics, and the like) that are often observed in conventionally cast composites. The cleanliness of the fracture surfaces can be directly attributed to the well controlled microstructures produced by the centrifugal casting process. In compression, the composite specimens failed in a manner that is typical of a brittle material. That is to say, the composite materials failed by cracks that propagated in the directions of the maximum shear stresses in the specimen (approximately at a 45° angle to the axis of the specimens).

Figure 11 — SEM electron micrographs of the tensile fracture surfaces.

In summary, therefore, the mechanical properties of the centrifugally cast specimens were evaluated as a function of materials structures and processing. The results show that a range of properties can be attained by adjusting the structures through processing. Centrifugal casting is therefore a valuable means to engineer the desired structures and mechanical properties of metal matrix composites. Overall results showed that the composite materials provided superior strength and modulus relative to the unreinforced aluminum both in tension and compression loadings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was sponsored by the NSWC contract N60921-89-C-0217 and by the Westinghouse IR&D funds. The Navy portion of this work was funded by the Office of Naval Technology (ONT) through the Weapons and Space Craft Materials Block Program. We would like to thank Mr. T. J. Devine of the Wisconsin Centrifugal Inc. for his assistance in conducting the laboratory experiments at the Westinghouse Science and Technology Center, and Mr. T. Klimowicz of the Dural Aluminum Composites Corporation for providing the chemical analysis of the composite samples and Dr. M. A. Burke of the Westinghouse Science & Technology Center for his valuable suggestions and comments.

4. REFERENCES

1. U.S. Patent Application, 70890 (1987), S. D. Karmarkar and A. P. Divecha (Naval Surface Warfare Center), "Centrifugal Casting of Composites."
2. S. D. Karmarkar and A. P. Divecha, Proc. of Tenth Annual Discontinuously Reinforced MMC Working Group Meeting, Park City, Utah, pp. 165-190, (1986).
3. L. Lajoie and M. Suery, ASM Conf. Proc., Eds. S. G. Fishman and A. K. Dhingra, Chicago, Illinois, pp. 15-20, (1988).
4. J. E. Hilliard and J. W. Cahn, Trans. AIME, 221, p. 809, (1961).

